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Potential Antifungal Compound from *Gliricidia Maculate* Leaf Extract against Pathogenic Fungi (*Colletotrichum Capsici*, *Fusarium Oxysporum* And *Cercospora Capsici*) on Chili Pepper

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Abstract

The reduction of Chili production has been witnessed over the decades due to phytopathogenic fungi infection. Most of the infection was affected by *Colletotrichum capsici*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Cercospora capsici*. Leaf extract of *Gliricidia maculate* contains active compound promising for altering synthetic fungicide. The secondary metabolite extracted from *Gliricidia maculate* Leaf suspected to be potential for bio fungicide. The aim of study was to investigate antifungal activity of *Gliricidia maculate* leaf extract for pathogenic fungal. Active compound was measured following Non Factorial Complete Random Design under various concentrations (10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90 and 100%) with 3 replications. The suppression process was observed from 20% of leaf extract against *Colletotrichum capsici*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Cercospora capsici* with the inhibitory percentage of 82.49% against *Colletotrichum capsici* while 40% of leaf extract for 84.67% and 87.73% against *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Cercospora capsici* respectively. The concentration of 20% gamal leaf extract and 40% of the inhibition of each fungus was equivalent to the Benlox 50 WP synthetic fungicide. *Gliricidia maculate* Leaf extract showed the suppression activity toward pathogenic fungi infection in Chili pepper.

Keywords: Leaf extract, Secondary metabolites, Suppression activity, Bio-fungicide

INTRODUCTION

Chili pepper production declined in most of region in Indonesia from decades. In North Sumatera, the it was reduced 8.72% from 14.123 ton in 2014. The major cause of this circumstance was associated to the prevalence and severity of three massive pathogenic fungi identified as *Colletotrichum capsici*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Cercospora capsici* (Astuti, 2019; Ferniah et al., 2018; Oo and Oh, 2016). They have typical symptom which indicates their infections on plant tissue surface. *Colletotrichum capsici* causing anthracnose was reported to be one of the most dangerous disease with the symptom including sunken necrotic tissues with concentric rings of acervuli and fused lesion. The infection could severely reduce quality and quantity of yield leading to economical loss. Wilt caused by *Fusarium oxysporum* appeared symptom such vein clearing, leaf yellowing, epinasty and stunting by penetrating root and intervening nutrition flow through plant vascular system (Ferniah et al., 2018). In several countries including Indonesia, leaf spot disease has also been major cause of crop loss which should be overcome comprehensively.

Secondary metabolite from plant extract is known to be effective active matter altering chemical fungicide. Several empirical studies revealed secondary metabolites extracted from various plant appeared inhibitory activity against pathogen such as bacteria, fungi, virus and insect. Crude extract from *P. sarmentosum* leaves appeared total inhibitory activity of mycelium growth of *C. gloeosporioides* and spore germination (Bussaman et al., 2012). About 5.6 mm which equal to 78.87% inhibitory activity was obtained from crude *Jatropha curcas* and ethanol extract when tested with *C. gloeosporioides* (Rahman et al., 2011). Several extract

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and crude from various plants have potential antifungal compound including *Plumbago indica*, *P. capensis*, *P. zeylanica*, *obacco leaf*, *keora seed*, *keora*, *mahogoni*, *gaint indian milky weed*, *garlic*, *ginger*, and *Ficus Septica* (Mukherjee et al., 2011; Saravanakumar et al., 2011; Sudirga et al., 2014). Nevertheless, broad spectrum antifungal compound from leaves extract has not been reported yet.

Photochemical analysis from *Gliricidia Maculate* was suspected to be containing high content of secondary metabolites including alkaloid, terpenoid, dan flavonoid. Those are universally known as biological active compound which have antifungal properties. One of those is Flavonoid which acts as signal and phytoalexin toward pathogen infection leading to plant fitness and resistance toward pathogen infection by modulating level of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in plant (Samanta et al., 2011; Weston and Mathesius, 2013). Generally, all bioactive compound could inhibit mycelial growth, germination and sporulation pathogenic fungi especially enzyme inhibition by compounds oxidation. We identified the phytochemical compound and elucidated the suppression activity of *Gliricidia Maculate* leaf extract against *Colletothricum capsici*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Cercospora capsicin*.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Sample Preparation

Three different fungi (*Colletothricum capsici*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Cercospora capsici*) were isolated from Chili fruit which shown certain symptom indicating the disease from Bandar Slamet District, Medan Estate. Meanwhile, *Gliricidia maculate* was collected from Sumber jaya district, langkat regency North Sumatera. About 3000 gr of *Gliricidia maculate* was grinded and air drying for several hours. The sample was then directly submerged in 15 L methanol for three days following filtering it using *vacuum rotary evaporator* for evaporation process. The process was connected to the storage for collecting leaf extract and mixed by distilled water for ration 1:1 (b/v) following storing it in 4°C.

In-vitro analysis was conducted using 10 different concentrations from 10 – 100% (10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90 and 100%) including one negative and positive control pH 7.0 (Table 1).

Table 1. The treatment for in-vitro analysis

Threatment (%)	Extract (mL)	Distillated water (mL)	PDA (gr)
ED ₀ (Con. +)		150	6
ED ₁ (Cont. -)		150	6
ED ₂	15	135	6
ED ₃	30	120	6
ED ₄	45	105	6
ED ₅	60	90	6
ED ₆	75	75	6
ED ₇	90	60	6
ED ₈	105	45	6
ED ₉	120	30	6
ED ₁₀	135	15	6
ED ₁₁	150	0	6

*) Benlox 50 WP 0,2%

Phytochemical analysis

Secondary metabolites contained in sample was analysis using certain procedure. the chemical compound was analyzed including Flavonoid, Tanin, Saponin, Alkaloida, Steroida/triterpenoid and Glicosida. Those active chemical compound analysis procedures were described by Marjoni (2016)

Antifungal bioassay from *Gliricidia maculate* Leaf Extract and Statistical Analysis

Analysis was conducted following Non-Factorial Complete Random Design with 144 plates in total. Fungi was cultured in solid medium containing above-mentioned concentrations. mycelial growth diameter of every fungi

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was measured every 2 days. Inhibition rate was measured following formula described by Marjoni (2016) 8 days after inoculation:

$$T = \frac{D_0 - D_n}{D_0} \times 100\%$$

Where, DO is the diameter of untreated fungi (Negative control), and Dn is the diameter of fungus on treatment. Each treatment was performed in 3 replications. The diameter of fungal mycelium was analyzed using SPSS presented with mean and standard deviation. Data from bioassay was processed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Significant differences from each treatment group were further processed using Duncan’s New Multiple Range Test (DNMRT) with a p<0.05 (Duncan, 1955).

Result

Phytochemical analysis of *Gliricidia maculate* leaf extract

Active compound of leaf Extract from the *Gliricidia maculate* leaf was identified before mixing it in culture medium. The phytochemical analysis result is presented in Tabel 1.

Table 2. Phytochemical analysis from *Gliricidia maculate* leaf extract

Phytochemical	Actual Result	Indication
Flavonoid	Yellow, orange and red was formed on amyl alcohol layer	+
Tannin	Green or Blue on mixture	+
Saponin	foam on solution	+
Alkaloid	2 out of 3 have settled bellow solution	+
Steroid/triterpenoid	Color transformed from purple to green	+
Glycoside	Violet ring was formed	+

(+) Present (-) Absent

Sample appeared positively indicated the present of active compounds. The chemical analysis determined that sample extract contains active chemical compound which is potentially used for natural bio fungicide against pathogenic fungi.

Determination of inhibitory effects of extracts against pathogenic fungal hyphal growth

Active compound is indicated by inhibitory effect on pathogenic fungi growth. The suppression activity from leaf extract is listed on Table 3.

Table 3. Inhibitory effect of *Gliricidia maculate* leaf extract of growth of pathogenic fungi

Treatment	Diameter zone of Inhibition													
	2 dpi		3 dpi		4 dpi		5 dpi		6 dpi		7 dpi		8 dpi	
ED ₀	1,48	B	2,53	C	3,32	C	3,53	C	4,17	C	5,12	C	5,72	C
ED ₁	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A
ED ₂	1,00	A	1,13	B	1,93	B	2,02	B	2,62	B	3,02	B	3,72	B
ED ₃	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A
ED ₄	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A
ED ₅	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A
ED ₆	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A
ED ₇	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A
ED ₈	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A
ED ₉	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A
ED ₁₀	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A
ED ₁₁	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A	1,00	A

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Based on the Tabel 3. Inhibitory effect was directly observed on 2 dpi where the effective concentration was 10% compare to negative control. when it is compared to the synthetic fungicide (0.2% Benlox), the treatment gave the same suppression effect.

Similar to *Colletotrichum Capsici*, others two fungi grown under treatment were also performed and shown the inhibition. The effective concentration of leaf extract for *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Cercospora capsici* was 40% (3 dpi) and 40% (6dpi) respectively (data not shown). the inhibitory percentage of in-vitro analysis on pathogenic fungal growth on 8 dpi is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Antifungal properties of *Gliricidia maculate* extract on pythopathogenic fugi

treatment	Inhibitory of <i>Gliricidia maculate</i> extract					
	<i>Colletotrichum capici</i>		<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>		<i>Cercospora capsici</i>	
ED0	0,00	B	0,00	E	0,00	E
ED1	82,49	A	84,67	A	87,73	A
ED2	34,93	C	37,32	D	52,96	D
ED3	82,49	A	44,64	C	73,21	C
ED4	82,49	A	69,36	B	86,5	B
ED5	82,49	A	84,67	A	87,73	A
ED6	82,49	A	84,67	A	87,73	A
ED7	82,49	A	84,67	A	87,73	A
ED8	82,49	A	84,67	A	87,73	A
ED9	82,49	A	84,67	A	87,73	A
ED10	82,49	A	84,67	A	87,73	A
ED11	82,49	A	84,67	A	87,73	A

The active compound of leaf extract shown the suppression activity in from low concentration. The extract Inhibited pathogenic fungi equal to inhibition percentage of synthetic fungicide in 82.49, 84.67 and 87.73% on 8 dpi against *Colletotrichum capici*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, and *Cercospora capsici* respectively. Visualization of bioassay is presented in Fig. 1

Figure 1. Visualization of antifungal assay on 8 dpi

Antifungal assay revealed the inhibitory effect from leaf extract toward three pathogenic fungal growths which was noticeably seen on figure 2. The Visualization could confirm the suppression activity from leaf extract. The color and diameter of those three fungi on control observed on 8 dpi shown inhibition activity on treatment compared to control.

Discussion

Gliricidia maculate has potential as antifungal compound. Based on phytochemical analysis listed in Tabel 1, it contains phytotoxins which suppress fungal growth. The secondary metabolites contained in its leaf have association for plant defense mechanism toward pathogen infection. These secondary metabolites are associated on survival and plant fitness (Pusztahelyi et al., 2015). Flavonoids, Polyphenol group, is known to alter microbial cell permeability causing structural protein deformation and dysfunction. Flavonoid was also reported its suppression property against *Fusarium oxysporum* (Middleton et al., 2000).

Saponnin plays significant role on antifungal activity in sample. This antifungal compounds activates the *phosphotyrosine kinase* and G-protein signaling pathway which then elevate ROS and Ca^{+} and leakage the cytosol (Ito et al., 2007). Furthermore, these secondary metabolites have saponification mechanism which leads to the lysis of fungal cell wall. As well as others metabolites, Tannin has superior features including on Binding protein, inhibiting enzyme catalyzing process particularly chitin synthesis, and substrate deprivation (Gurjar et al., 2012; Watson and Preedy, 2008).

Antifungal compound contained in sample played significant role on inhibitory activity. This was statistically tested in this study and shown significant result (Table 3 and Tabel 4) which is visualized in Fig.1. there were series of study regarding to antifungal property from leave extract. Antifungal property of *Eucalyptus* leaf extract was tested with *Penicillium funiculosum* with *Minimal Inhibitory Concentration* (MIC) and *Minimal Fungicidal Concentration* (MFC) value of 0.15 ± 0.03 mg/mL and 0.26 ± 0.01 mg/mL (Elansary et al., 2017). In another study, the extract of *Amaranthus retroflexus* was degraded to be Silver nanoparticle revealed antifungal property against *Macrophomina phaseolina*, for $71.09\% \pm 1.41\%$ and *Fusarium oxysporum* $53.83\% \pm 1.04\%$ (Devi et al., 2019). This study revealed that maximum inhibition against tested pathogenic fungi was 87.73% on *Fusarium oxysporum* which is double the inhibition with Silver nanoparticle from *Amaranthus retroflexus*. From this study we firmly believe that this potential active compound contained in *Gliricidia maculate* leaf extract could substitute to synthetic fungicide such as Benlox 50 WP 0,2%.

Conclusion

It is concluded that Leaf extract of *Gliricidia maculate* has active compound which could possible as biocontrol for phytopathogenic fungi which has equal effect to Benlox 50 WP 0,2%. The inhibitory activity reported in this study was 82 – 87%.

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